

GROWTH, DEVELOPMENT, AND YIELD ACCUMULATION PROCESSES IN DIFFERENT VARIETIES OF QUINCE

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Abstract: This article presents the results of a study conducted to select the best among 26 local and introduced quince varieties under the low-fertility, rocky-gravel soil conditions of the Fergana region. The varieties Olmabehi, Nonbehi, Turush Bukharskaya, and Krimskaya rannyaya exhibited bud swelling on average 5-6 days earlier, indicating relatively early maturation. Compared to the standard Izobilnaya variety, the Kolkhoznaya and Olmabehi varieties produced an additional yield of 3.3 and 23.8 centners, respectively.

Keywords: local, introduction, quince, bud swelling, flowering rate, yield potential, productivity, additional yield, fruit taste, total sugar content, fruit quality.

Introduction: The quince, due to its small branches, early fruiting, consistent annual yield, long-term fruit storage, and the abundance of various beneficial substances in its fruit, is considered one of the most valuable types of fruit. Its significance for human health further elevates its status. Consequently, scientific research on quince varieties and the expansion of quince orchards has become a pressing issue.

Research Methodology

The studies conducted to evaluate local and introduced quince varieties and to identify those with superior valuable agronomic traits were based on the accepted methodology (Sedov, 1999). The mathematical analysis was performed using B.A. Dospexov's method (Dospexov, 1985). The research was carried out at the Fergana Scientific Experimental Station of the Scientific Research Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture, and Winemaking named after Academician Mahmud Mirzaev. The study was conducted in a quince collection orchard located in low-fertility, rocky-gravel soil conditions.

Analysis and Results

Phenological observations indicate that bud swelling in quince varieties occurred from March 18-26 in 2018, March 14-24 in 2019, and March 16-26 in

2020 (Table 1). It was found that compared to the control variety, Izobilnaya (March 20-23), the varieties Olmabehi (March 14-22), Nonbehi (March 14-18), and Krimskaya rannyaya (March 15-21) exhibited bud swelling on average 5-6 days earlier. This trend was also nearly maintained during the flowering process.

Specifically, over the three years of observations, full bloom in the Izobilnaya (control) variety was recorded around April 5-10, while Olmabehi bloomed from April 6-10, Nonbehi from April 4-8, Otlichnitsa from April 5-10, Chuchuk krupnaya from April 4-7, and Yerevan from April 7-9.

The three-year evaluation of flowering levels showed that the varieties Izobilnaya (3.8-4.3 points), Olmabehi (3.4-4.1 points), Bahri (3.5-4.2 points), Azerbaijan (3.3-4.1 points), Nonbehi (4-4.2 points), Myagkoplodnaya №9 (3.6-4.2 points), Chuchuk krupnaya (3.7-4.1 points), Sovxoznaya (3.8-4.2 points), Urojaynaya (3.8-4.2 points), Shirin (3.8-4.2 points), and Otlichnitsa (3.5-4.5 points) exhibited higher flowering scores than other varieties.

The lowest flowering scores were recorded in the varieties Yerevan (3.1-3.2 points), Asinovskaya (3.1-3.4 points), and Konservnaya (3.2-3.5 points). The analysis of flowering levels provides a basis for predicting higher productivity in the above-mentioned quince varieties.

Table 1. Flowering and ripening periods of various quince varieties

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Variety	Bud Swelling start			Full Bloom period			Flowering Intensity			Mass Ripening period			Yield Capacity points		
	2018	2019	2020	2018	2019	2020	2018	2019	2020	2018	2019	2020	2018	2019	2020
2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
Izobilnaya(control)	23.03	20.03	23.03	10.04	8.04.	5.04.	4.3	4	3.8	28.09	22.09.	16.09.	4	3	3.5
Nargush	23.03	14.03	18.03	10.04	8.04.	5.04.	3.6	3.3	3.4	12.09	7.09.	5.09.	3.6	2.9	3.3
Sovxoznaya	22.03	17.03	21.03	9.04	10.04.	6.04.	3.3	3.3	3.6	29.09	22.09.	18.09.	4.2	3.8	4
Krupnoplodnaya	24.03	20.03	22.03	12.04	11.04.	7.04.	3.3	3.1	3.9	27.09	19.09.	14.09.	3.9	3.4	3.5
Samarkandskaya	21.03	17.03	19.03	9.04	10.04.	9.04.	3.3	3.1	3.7	23.09	21.09.	15.09	3.4	3.6	3.5
Konservnaya	26.03	24.03	26.03	12.04	9.04.	8.04.	3.5	3.4	3.2	29.09	26.09.	18.09	3.5	3.5	3.5
Olma behi	22.03	14.03	16.03	10.04	6.04.	6.04.	3.4	4	4.1	19.09	16.09.	12.09.	4.3	4.1	4.2
Kolxoznitsa	24.03	17.03	18.03	11.04	9.04.	8.04.	3.4	3.4	3.5	28.09	25.09.	17.09.	4	3.3	3.6
Samarkand pozdnyaya	20.03	19.03	22.03	7.04	8.04.	7.04.	3.9	3	3.8	29.09	26.09.	20.09.	3.5	3.2	3.3
Krymskaya rannyaya	21.03	15.03	18.03	8.04	9.04.	6.04.	3.7	3.6	3.6	15.09	17.09.	13.09	3	3.4	3.2
Triumf	23.03	20.03	21.03	9.04	7.04.	8.04.	3.5	3.2	3	3.10.	30.09.	22.09	3.4	3.1	3.3
Nikitinskaya rannyaya	22.03	18.03	20.03	9.04	10.04.	6.04.	3.8	3.5	3.6	16.09	12.09.	10.09.	3.5	3.7	3.5
Azerbaijan	21.03	19.03	22.03	10.04	9.04.	9.04.	3.7	4.1	3.3	18.09	14.09.	11.09.	3.6	3.6	3.5
Badalskaya pozdnyaya	23.03	21.03	23.03	11.04	11.04.	7.04.	3.9	3.5	3.5	29.09	27.09.	19.09.	3.5	3.2	3.3
Dushistaya	22.03	17.03	19.03	9.04	7.04.	6.04.	3.3	3.8	3.4	22.09	17.09.	14.09.	3	3.4	3.2
Nonbehi	18.03	14.03	17.03	8.04	8.04.	4.04.	4	4.2	4	13.09.	9.09.	3.09.	4.2	3.5	3.7
Asinovskaya №3	23.03	16.03	17.03	11.04	11.04.	9.04.	3.2	3.1	3.4	30.09	29.09.	20.09.	2.9	3.5	3.2
Bereskaya	24.03	20.03	22.03	13.04	10.04.	8.04.	3.9	3.2	3.3	28.09	23.09.	16.09.	3	3.1	3.2
Bahri	22.03	18.03	19.03	10.04	10.04.	6.04.	3.8	3.5	3.5	19.09	13.09.	11.09.	4.3	3.5	3.7
Myagkoplodnaya №9	20.03	17.03	18.03	8.04	6.04.	7.04.	3.6	4.2	4	13.09.	9.09.	4.09.	4	3.2	3.6
Otlichnitsa	21.03	18.03	20.03	9.04	10.04.	5.04.	4	3.7	3.8	20.09	16.09.	13.09.	4.5	3.5	4
Chuchuk krupnaya	19.03	16.03	16.03	7.04	7.04.	4.04.	3.7	4.1	4	15.09.	11.09.	9.09.	3.9	3.5	3.7
Shirin	23.03	20.03	20.03	10.04	9.04.	7.04.	4	3.1	3.9	18.09.	11.09.	8.09.	4.2	3.8	4
Urojaynaya	26.03	22.03	22.03	9.04	8.04.	9.04.	4.2	3.8	3.9	30.09.	26.09.	17.09	4.3	3.7	4
Maselnaya rannyaya	24.03	21.03	18.03	11.04	11.04.	8.04.	3.2	4.1	3.2	9.09.	8.09.	6.09.	3.8	3.7	3.7
Erevan	22.03	19.03	23.03	8.04	9.04.	7.04.	3.1	3.2	3.2	1.10.	29.09.	20.09.	3.2	2.9	3.2

Among the studied varieties, early ripening characteristics were exhibited by Maselnaya Rannyaya, Nargush, Myagkoplodnaya, Nonbehi, Chuchuk Krupnaya, and Nikitskaya Rannyaya. The mass ripening period for these varieties occurred from September 5 to 16. Relatively late-ripening varieties such as Urojaynaya, Yerevan, Konservnaya, Asinovskaya №3, Samarkand Pozdnyaya, Triumf, and Badalskaya Pozdnyaya recorded mass ripening between September 19 and October third.

Three-year assessments of yield potential among quince varieties indicated that Izobilnaya, Sovxoznaya, Olmabehi, Nonbehi, Bahri, Myagkoplodnaya №9, Otlichnitsa, and Urojaynaya varieties were superior to all other varieties.

According to the three-year analysis of quince yield, the varieties Izobilnaya (control), Sovxoznaya, Konservnaya, Olmabehi, Otlichnitsa, and Urojaynaya excelled in terms of fruit yield per tree (see Table 2). The quantity of fruit harvested from each tree of these varieties ranged from 34.4 to 40 kg. The patterns of flowering and yield potential were also reflected in the yield per hectare. For instance, the Olmabehi variety produced an average yield of 200 quintals per year, yielding an additional 23.8 quintals compared to the Izobilnaya standard variety. The Sovxoznaya variety yielded 177 quintals, with an additional yield of 0.8 quintals; the Konservnaya variety yielded 179.5 quintals, with an additional yield of 3.3 quintals; and the Urojaynaya variety

yielded 177.5 quintals, with an additional yield of 1.2 quintals. Thus, mathematical analysis confirmed that additional yield was achieved with the Konservnaya and Olmabehi varieties. However, several local and introduced quince varieties showed lower productivity compared to the standard variety Izobilnaya in the low-fertility, rocky soils of the Fergana region. Compared to the Izobilnaya variety, the Yerevan variety yielded 78 quintals less, the Bereskaya variety yielded 75 quintals less, and the Asinovskaya variety yielded 72 quintals less.

One of the important quality indicators of quince is the weight of an individual fruit (see Table 3). For example, the standard Izobilnaya variety has a fruit weight of 188.7 grams. significant superiority compared to the Izobilnaya variety was observed in the Sovxoznaya (251.1 g), Krupnoplodnaya (268.1 g), Bahri (260.7 g), Samarkandskaya (267.3 g), and Kolxoznitsa (243.9 g) varieties.

Table 2. Productivity of various quince varieties

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№	Variety	Yield per tree (kg)				Yield per hectare (s/ha)				Difference from Control (s/ha)			
		2018	2019	2020	average	2018	2019	2020	average	2018	2019	2020	average
1	Izobilnaya(control)	40,3	35,6	29,8	35,2	201,5	178,2	149,0	176,2	0	0	0	0
2	Nargush	37,0	34,0	29,0	33,3	185,0	170,9	145,0	167,0	-16,5	-7,3	-4,0	-9,3
3	Sovxoznaya	42,0	33,2	31,0	35,4	210,0	166,0	155,0	177,0	8,5	-12,2	6,0	0,8
4	Krupnoplodnaya	39,3	24,2	25,6	29,7	196,5	121,0	128,0	148,5	-5,0	-57,2	-21,0	-27,7
5	Samarkandskaya	33,6	29,6	26,6	29,9	168,0	148,6	123,0	146,5	-33,5	-29,6	-26,0	-29,7
6	Konservnaya	37,3	34,6	35,8	35,9	186,5	173,0	179,0	179,5	-15,0	-5,2	30,0	3,3
7	Oлма behi	43,0	39,2	37,8	40,0	215,0	196,0	189,0	200,0	13,5	17,8	40,0	23,8
8	Kolxoznitsa	40,0	30,6	20,2	30,3	200,0	153,2	101,0	151,4	-1,5	-25,0	-48,0	-24,8
9	Samarkand	37,7	17,6	24,0	26,4	188,5	88,3	120,0	132,3	-13,5	-89,9	-29,0	-44,1
10	Крымская ранняя	25,0	24,6	23,2	24,3	125,0	123,4	116,0	121,5	-76,5	-54,8	-33,0	-54,8
11	Триумф	31,7	22,2	20,2	24,7	158,5	111,2	101,0	123,6	-43,5	-67,0	-48,0	-52,8
12	Nikitinskaya	32,3	30,6	24,8	29,2	161,5	153,3	124,0	146,3	-40,0	-24,9	-25,0	-30,0
13	Azerbaijan	38,0	31,0	18,6	29,2	190,0	155,0	93,0	146,0	-11,5	-23,2	-56,0	-30,2
14	Badalskaya	21,2	29,2	19,6	23,3	176,5	146,2	98,0	140,2	-25,0	-32,0	-51,0	-36,0
15	Dushistaya	14,4	18,4	23,6	18,8	119,9	92,7	118,0	110,2	-81,6	-85,5	-31,0	-66,0
16	Nonbehi	40,7	17,0	27,6	28,4	203,5	85,1	138,0	142,2	2,0	-93,1	-11,0	-34,0
17	Asinovskaya №3	22,0	23,5	16,8	20,8	110,0	117,5	84,0	103,8	-91,5	-60,7	-65,0	-72,4
18	Bereskaya	23,3	19,8	16,4	19,8	116,5	99,2	82,0	99,2	-85,0	-79,0	-63,0	-75,7
19	Bahri	42,7	25,2	15,4	27,8	213,5	126,4	77,0	139,0	12,0	-51,8	-72,0	-37,3
20	Myagkoplodnaya №9	24,8	21,6	20,6	22,3	206,5	108,3	103,0	139,3	5,0	-69,9	-46,0	-37,0
21	Otlichnitsa	44,5	30,8	28,0	34,4	222,5	154,2	140,0	172,2	21,0	-24,0	-9,0	-4,0
22	Chuchuk krupnaya	39,6	21,8	29,8	30,4	198,0	109,5	149,0	152,2	-3,5	-68,7	0,0	-24,1
23	Shirin	41,5	31,5	25,2	32,7	207,5	157,1	126,0	163,5	6,0	-21,1	-23,0	-12,7
24	Urojaynaya	41,6	34,0	30,8	35,5	208,0	170,4	154,0	177,5	6,5	-7,8	5,0	1,2
25	Maselnaya rannaya	37,3	25,8	12,8	25,3	186,5	129,8	154,0	156,8	-15,0	-48,4	5,0	-19,5
26	Erevan	20,0	24,0	14,5	19,5	100,0	120,0	72,5	97,5	-101,5	-58,2	-76,5	-78,7

(Average three-year NSR05 is 2.2 s/ha, NSR05 is 1.4%).

Fruits with smaller size and weight include the Maselnaya rannaya (146.5 g) and Urojaynaya (152 g) varieties.

Regarding the taste of the fruit, the Izobilnaya, Sovxoznaya, Krupnoplodnaya, Olmabehi, Samarkandskaya, Samarkand pozdneyaya, Nonbehi, and Shirin varieties received high ratings (4.0-4.5 points). The total sugar content in the fruit was found to be high (13.0-14.1 percent) in the Izobilnaya, Sovxoznaya,

Shirin, Krupnoplodnaya, Samarkandskaya, Samarkand pozdnyaya, and Kolxoznitsa varieties.

Conclusion and Recommendations: Based on the research results, a group of superior varieties with valuable economic traits was selected from local and introduced varieties. Therefore, for newly established quince orchards, high-yielding varieties with fruit quality characteristics that meet export requirements such as Olmabehi, Izobilnaya, Konservnaya, Krupnoplodnaya, Samarkandskaya, Samarkand pozdnyaya, and Shirinbehi are recommended.

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